

Table 1. Effect of urea, boric acid, and GA₃ sprays at various stages on seed yield of CMS rice line IR54752A. IRRRI, 1987 WS.

Chemical and concentration	Seed yield (kg/ha) with spraying at			
	Full booting	Initial heading	20% heading	Mean seed yield (kg/ha)
Control (no spray)	376	381	443	400
GA ₃ 30 ppm	380	386	487	418
GA ₃ 60 ppm	370	421	501	431
Boric acid 0.5%	334	353	497	395
Boric acid 1.0%	391	347	491	410
Urea 1.0%	394	436	495	442
Urea 1.5%	397	457	536	463
Mean	377	397	493	
CV (%)	16.6			

Table 2. Effect of urea, boric acid, KNO₃, and GA₃ sprays at various growth stages on seed yield of CMS rice line IR54752A. IRRRI, 1988 DS.

Chemical and concentration	Seed yield (kg/ha) with spraying at			
	Full booting	Initial heading	20% heading	Mean seed yield (kg/ha)
Control	478	472	392	447
GA ₃ (90 ppm)	562	570	452	528
Urea (2%)	621	511	565	566
Boric Acid (1.5%)	625	500	534	553
KNO ₃ (2%)	577	509	431	506
Mean	572	512	475	—
CV (%)	7.7			

Paired comparisons

	LSD	
	1%	5%
1. Between main plot means (averaged over all subplot treatments)	127.37	55.22
2. Between subplot means (averaged over all main plot treatments)	69.88	49.84
3. Between subplot means at the same main plot treatment	121.03	86.33

world. We tested their efficacy in hybrid rice seed production.

Field experiments in 1987-88 at IRRRI involved various concentrations and times of application of urea, boric acid KNO₃, and GA₃ on CMS line IR54752A and its maintainer IR54752B planted at a female:male row ratio of 8:2 in a 10.8-m² plot. The experiments were in a split-plot design with growth stages as main plot and chemical treatments as subplots, with three replications.

In the 1987 WS experiment, seed yields of treated and control plots were not significantly different (Table 1). In

1988 dry season (DS), 2% KNO₃ was tested with selected concentrations of GA₃, urea, and boric acid. Seed yields of IR54752A significantly differed (Table 2). When sprayed at full booting, boric acid (1.5%) gave the highest yield (625 kg/ha) of the CMS line, followed by urea (2%) spray (621 kg/ha). When sprayed at initial heading, GA₃ (90 ppm) gave the highest seed yield (570 kg/ha). Urea (2%) (565 kg/ha) and boric acid (1.5%) (534 kg/ha) sprays at 20% heading gave significantly higher seed yields. On the whole, urea (1.5 to 2.0%) or boric acid (1.5%) sprayed at full

booting, initial heading, or 20% heading was as effective as GA₃. Neither urea nor boric acid increased plant height of either CMS or maintainer lines.

Urea, boric acid, and GA₃ application gave seed sets of 10.7, 9.3, and 11.0%, respectively, compared with 7.7% for control during the DS experiment. It appears that increased seed yields due to application of growth chemicals in DS were due to increased seed set. Even though chemical application increased seed set in WS, seed yield was not increased significantly, indicating a negative effect of some other factor.

The overall results indicate that 1.5-2% urea or 1.5% boric acid can substitute for GA₃ in hybrid rice seed production. □

Expression and segregation of isozyme genes in rice microspore-derived calli

E. Guiderdoni, B. delos Reyes, and G. Vergara, Plant Breeding Department, IRRRI

Whether anther culture (AC) derivatives represent a random gametic array of the microspore pool is of primary importance in applying this methodology to rice breeding. To test the randomness of in vitro induction, we studied segregations of heterozygous markers among AC derivatives.

Table 1. Isozyme genes expressed in the microspore-derived callus of rice.^a IRRRI, 1988.

<i>Adh-1</i>	<i>Amp-1</i>
<i>Sdh-1</i>	<i>Amp-2</i>
<i>Icd-1</i>	<i>Amp-3</i>
<i>Cat-1</i>	<i>Amp-4</i>
<i>Pgi-1</i>	<i>Acp-1</i>
<i>Pgi-2</i>	<i>Acp-2</i>
<i>Pgd-1</i>	<i>Acp-3</i>
<i>Pgd-2</i>	<i>Acp-4</i>
<i>Got-1</i>	<i>Est-1</i>
<i>Got-2</i>	<i>Est-2</i>
<i>Mal-1</i>	<i>Est-9</i>

^a *Pox-2* and *Est-7* never appeared and *Est-5* showed an altered expression in our experiments. Data recorded on the following varieties and crosses: Taipei 309, Aus 454, Fujiminori, Tetep, Dinorado/BR319-1, UPLRi-5/CNA4121, IRAT177/Apura.

Table 2. Comparison of segregation for 8 heterozygous isozyme markers among F₂ plants, and anther cultured-derived calli of the cross IRAT177/Apura.^a IRR1, 1988.

Materials	Locus							
	<i>Icd-1</i>	<i>Pgi-1</i>	<i>Sdh-1</i>	<i>Acp-1</i>	<i>Est-9</i>	<i>Amp-2</i>	<i>Pgd-1</i>	<i>Est-1</i>
IRAT177	F	F	F	F	S	S	F	A
Apura	S	S	S	S	F	F	S	P
F ₂ progeny ^b	54:95:40	45:94:50	43:102:44	49:93:43	57:87:43	50:74:64	63:71:44	41:148
	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	S**	S**	ns
AC-derived calli ^b	234:210	182:264	216:226	92:90	214:186	186:258	293:137	135:115
	ns	S**	ns	ns	ns	S**	S**	ns

^aThe allele designations adopted are F (fast) vs S (slow) when the parents differed in the migration speed of the allozymes, and A (absence) vs P (presence) when the parents differed in the presence of a band. ^bSegregation of isozyme phenotypes following the order SS:SF:FF or AA:AP:PP for the F₂ progeny and SS:FF or AA:PP for the AC-derived calli. By the *Chi Square Tests for Homogeneity*, F₂ fit a 1:2:1 or a 1:3 segregation; AC-derived calli fit a 1:1 segregation. S** = significant at the 5% level, ns = not significant.

In the F₁s involving distantly related rice varieties, a large number of heterozygous isozyme markers exist. Segregation of such markers can be surveyed in AC plants and in AC calli; calli are produced in larger numbers.

The isozyme genes listed in Table 1 have been found to be reliably expressed among microspore-derived calli. We utilized them as efficient markers in detecting in vitro selection occurring during the rice AC process. Table 2

displays segregation data of 8 isozyme markers among microspore calli and F₂ plants derived from a japonica × indica cross. In addition to the deviations in both F₂ plants and AC calli that are probably due to the hybrid breakdown that occurs in crosses between distantly related varieties in rice, the AC process itself seems to induce a slight deviation at the *Pgi-1* locus toward the japonica allele. This suggests that the hybrid

sterility breakdown that hampers the use of japonica × indica crosses in rice conventional breeding may also affect doubled haploid breeding. It also indicates that AC calli do not represent a fully random array of this modified gametic pool. Isozymes appear to be efficient markers for detecting in vitro selection occurring during the AC process, from the callus stage through the regenerated plant level. □

Esterase isozyme as a marker in in vitro studies of rice

M. Maheswaran and S. R. S. Rangasamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

Isozymes can be used as markers during morphogenesis in in vitro studies. We studied the banding pattern of esterase isozymes in 21-d-old callus and regenerating callus of rice —*Oryza spontanea*, *O. glaberrima*, and *O. sativa* (cultivars Co 43, IR50, and IR1552).

The esterase enzyme was extracted using 0.2 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 6.0) containing 0.006 M β-mercaptoethanol. The technique was vertical acrylamide gel electrophoresis using 8% acrylamide. The Tris (0.005 M) and glycine (0.038 M) mixture used as gel and electrode buffer had pH 8.3. Zymograms were revealed by staining with α-naphthyl acetate in acetone and fast blue RR salt mixture in sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.2).

The similarities and dissimilarities in the zymograms of *O. spontanea*, *O. glaberrima*, and *O. sativa* show the species relationships of *Oryza*.

The electrophoresis of 21-d-old calli induced in Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium—each liter with 2 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxy-acetic acid (2,4-D) and 0.5 mg kinetin—showed 3 common groups of fast-migrating bands in all 5 genotypes (see figure). An additional fast-migrating band observed in *O. spontanea* was absent in the other genotypes.

In the zymogram of regenerating calli in MS medium—with 1 mg kinetin and 1 mg naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) per liter of the medium—*O. sativa* cultivars IR50 and IR1552 had similar banding patterns different from those of *O. spontanea* and *O. glaberrima*. *O. sativa* cultivar Co 43 had an additional band as well as the bands observed in IR50 and IR1552. *O. glaberrima* had an additional slow-migrating band not observed in *O. spontanea* but present in Co 43. Callus induction and plant

Zymogram of esterase isozymes of 5 *Oryza* genotypes, Tamil Nadu, India. 1 = *O. spontanea*, 2 = *O. glaberrima*, 3 = *O. sativa* Co 43, 4 = IR50, and 5 = IR1552.